

CLINICAL EVALUATION OF YASHTIMADHU GHRITA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF PARIKARTIKA (FISSURE-IN-ANO): A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Parikartika is a frequently encountered and painful anorectal disorder that closely resembles fissure-in-ano. It has been described by Acharyas as a complication (Vyapad) of Vamana, Virechana, and Basti procedures. In the modern era, rapid lifestyle changes—such as sedentary occupations, increased stress, irregular dietary patterns, and disturbed sleep habits—have contributed to a steady rise in lifestyle-related disorders, including anorectal conditions. Clinically, Parikartika is characterized primarily by *Kartanavat Vedana* (cutting-type pain) in the *Guda Pradesh* (anal region). Similarly, fissure-in-ano is defined as a condition marked by severe pain and bleeding per rectum during and after defecation. The most common cause is trauma to the anal canal due to the passage of hard stools. In Ayurvedic management, Acharyas have advocated the use of *Madhura*, *Snigdha*, and *Sheeta Dravyas*

both internally and locally. These are administered in forms such as Piccha Basti, Madhura Kashaya Dravya Siddha Basti, and Yashtimadhu Taila Basti for effective management of the condition.

KEYWORDS: Parikartika, fissure-in-ano, yashtimadhu ghrita, krtanvat vedana.

INTRODUCTION

The condition fissure-in-ano, commonly encountered in ano rectal practice has similar

location, pathology and predominant features of parikartika like excruciating pain, constipation, stool streaked with blood etc.^[1] Thus it is evident that parikartika can be correlated with fissure-in-ano mentioned in modern science. The disease Parikartika is presented with krtanvat vedana in guda pradesha as the main symptom. Acute and chronic, pain and bleeding are two main symptoms of this condition, pain is sometimes intolerable.^[2] Fissure-in-ano occurs most commonly in midline posteriorly. In males, usually occur in the midline posteriorly-90%, and less common anteriorly-10%. In females in midline posteriorly-60% and anteriorly-40%.^[3] According to modern treatment of acute fissure-in- ano is analgesic, stool softener and soothing ointment and surgical treatment is anal dilatation, sphincterotomy, fissurectomy are there but there are many complications of these procedures like recurrence, incontinence and pruritis.^[4] The factors responsible for Parikartika are found as Basti-Virechana Vyapad (Complication of the Basti and Virechana procedures), Arsha (piles), Atisara, Grahani, etc.^[5]

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

1. To review the fissure in ano in ayurved classics.
2. To study the effect of Yashtimadhu ghrita in the fissure in ano.

CASE REPORT

Present complaints- A 38 Years old Female patient having burning sensation after defecation, constipation, hard stool, strike wise bleeding per anum since 15 days came to OPD of Ayurveda Rugnalaya for diagnosis and management.

CLINICAL FINDINGS

Shool (pain) Burning sensation Bleeding per anum.

PHYSICAL EXAMINATION

The physical examination of the patient revealed temperature of 98.20F, pulse – 78/min, respiratory rate of 19/min, blood pressure of 120/70 mmHg, and oxygen saturation.

Ashtavidha Pariksha of patient revealed Nadi (pulse) was of Vata pradhana (dominant) pitta, Asmyak mal,. pravartana (hard stool), Samyak mutra pravartana (Normal urine), Sama jivha (White coated tongue), Samyak kshudha (Normal Appetite), Samyak trishna (Normal thirst), Samyak drika and was of Madhyam (Average) Akriti (Built). Routine investigations were done which are within normal limits and are as follows Hb- 11 gm% ; WBC - 5300 /cumm;

RBC - 4800/cumm; Blood sugar level (fasting) – 96 mg/dl; Blood sugar level (post prandial) – 130 mg/dl; HbsAg – Non Reactive; HIV – Non reactive.

LOCAL EXAMINATION

Site – Anal region Fissure groove seen Active bleeding Tenderness present

Per rectal examination – spasm

Materials

Yashtimadhu Bharad, Goghrita, water.

METHODOLOGY

Method of preparation

Yashtimadhu Ghrita was prepared by snehapak vidhi according to sushruta samhita chikitsa sthan chp 31 Snehopayogik chikitsa adhyay(6) . Proportions used were (1:4:16}

1-part Yashtimadhu Bharad; 4 parts =Goghrita; 16 parts = Water

Yashtimadhu kwatha is prepared with the moola of yashtimadhu. 1 part of Yashtimadhu Bharad and 16 parts of water taken in a vessel and boiled together till it reduced to Chaturamsha i.e. $\frac{1}{4}$ of the quantity. This is subjected to filtration. To this than 4 parts of Goghrita was added to the Yashtimadhu kwath & cooked over mandagni till only ghrita part remains. Afterwards Yashtimadhu ghrita was collected and measured. Then Yashtimadhu ghrita 10gm was filled into aluminium tubes with nozzle from the back side of the tube (open side) after filling the ghrita into tubes crimping was done in crimping machine and tube was sealed and labelled as Yashtimadhu Ghrita.

Table no. 1: Timeline of treatment.

Sr. No.	Oral medication	Dose	Anupana	Treatment duration
1.	Triphala guggule	250mg	Luke warm water	01 month
2.	Tab. Kultab	-	Luke warm water	01 month
3.	Tab.zerdol p	-	water	03 days

Table no. 2: Timeline of treatment.

Sr. No.	Local application	Action	Treatment duration
1.	Yashtimadhu ghrita	For healing	01 month

Advice- sitz bath with haridra churna. Total treatment duration is 1 month. Follow Up and Outcomes –

Table no. 3: Gradation of Symptoms.

Sr. No.	Symptoms	Grade No.0	Grade No.1	Grade No.2	Grade No.3	Grade No.4
1.	Shoola	No Shool	Occasional	Mild	Moderate	Severe
2.	Raktastrava (Bleeding Per Anum)	No (Raktastrava (Bleeding Per Anum)	Occasional	Mild	Moderate	Severe
3.	Tenderness	No Tenderness	Occasional	Mild	Moderate	Severe
4.	Burning Sensation After Defecation	No Burning Sensation After Defecation	Occasional	Mild	Moderate	Severe

Table no. 4: Changes in symptoms before and after treatment.

Sr. No.	Symptoms	Before treatment	After days	After 7 days	After 10 days	After 13 days	After treatment
1.	Shoola	4	3	3	2	1	0
2.	Raktastrava (Bleeding Per Anum)	4	2	2	1	1	0
3.	Tenderness	4	2	2	1	1	0
4.	Burning Sensation After Defecation	4	2	2	1	1	0

Fig. 1: Before Treatment. Fig. 2: After Treatment.

DISCUSSION

Yashtimadhu is the owner of the properties Madhura Rasa, Madhur Vipaka, Sheet Virya, and Vata Pittashamak.^[7] Additionally, Yashtimadhu has property in Vranaropana and Vrana Shodhana.^[8] Be Ghrita has a calming effect, forms a thin film layer. over them, and then permits early skin epithelization. The therapeutic, antiulcerogenic, anti- inflammatory, and skin regeneration properties of Yashrimadhu have been demonstrated.^[9] Sodium Glycyrrhizate has anti-ulcer properties and promoted skin regeneration.^[10] Asparagine is a type of amino acid that acts as an analgesic (a natural painkiller) and an anti-inflammatory agent. Glycyrrhizine is a saponin that is frequently used as an anti- inflammatory agent.

According to certain reports, the Vednashamak effect of Yashtimadhu Ghrit Local application without using also causes a reduction in pain. Along with reducing pain, it also serves an Vatahara, Pitta Shamak, Ropaka, Dahashamak, and Stambhak in Vrana.^[11]

CONCLUSION

The cost-efficient and successful treatment for fissures in ano is pichu with Yashtimadhu ghrita. The average time it took for Fissure in ano symptoms to go away was 12 days, which is shorter than the time needed for surgery and post-operative care. The pichu can be given at home by family members or the patient themselves, cutting down on time, money, and treatment resistance. With Yashtimadhu ghrita in an acute fissure in ano, surgery can be avoided.

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